

REMARKS ON LEGAL DISCOURSE

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Annotation. This article talks about legal linguistics, legal discourse, subject in legal discourse, materials for analyzing the subject, place and essence of legal discourse in anthropolinguistics, which is formed at the intersection of discourse, linguistics and jurisprudence.

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о юридической лингвистике, юридическом дискурсе, субъекте в юридическом дискурсе, материалах для анализа предмета, места и сущности юридического дискурса в антрополингвистике, которая формируется на стыке дискурса, лингвистики и юриспруденции.

Keywords: discourse, legal discourse, linguistic entity, text, legal discourse, problem, anthropolinguistics

Ключевые слова: дискурс, юридический дискурс, языковая сущность, текст, юридический дискурс, проблема, антрополингвистик.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the rise of legal consciousness, the consideration of laws and decisions by citizens has put important tasks before linguists and lawyers that need to be studied. The study of linguistics at a new stage has become a solution to many problems. The concept of "discourse" entered our linguistics as language and speech became different.. This term was used for the first time in 1952 in the article of Discourse Analysis by Z. Harris. The concept of discourse has been interpreted differently by different linguists and there is still no clear rule.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Zvegintsev evaluated discourse as a linguistic area hidden behind clouds [Zvegintsev 1976:170], while Arutyunova considered discourse as a text together with non-linguistic factors (pragmatic, socio-cultural, spiritual); the text viewed from the point of view of the event; speech considered as a purposeful social action [Arutyunova 1990:136-137] states.

The study and use of this term has become widespread in the last 20 years. Discussions related to discourse in Uzbek linguistics are more common in the works of Sh. provides. Currently, it is recognized that only discourse has such integrity.

And Kubryakova comes to the conclusion that there is no generally accepted definition of discourse during the current development of Linguistics [Kubryakova 2000:6].

Despite this, many scientific works on discourse have been carried out in our linguistics. Several types of discourse have been identified: artistic discourse, political discourse, rhetorical discourse, media discourse, newspaper discourse, legal discourse, and others.

At the intersection of language and jurisprudence, several fields emerged, and this was a necessity. Because studying, observing and finding solutions to legal texts created legal linguistics. Semantic-stylistic analysis of legal texts began.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The introduction of new value guidelines into the social environment led to the fundamental individualization of society, the sharp differentiation of society, the establishment and development of the concept of the individual. Language became the main means of communication, the means of expressing the attitude to the reality of the new society, the environment of working relationships was formed in the discourse. It is known that the law effectively uses language and speech to fulfill its tasks. In addition to words, semantic relations in the text have attracted the attention of jurists. He became interested in what was written in the laws and how they were understood.

Language and speech facts are studied, legal field and level of meta-information are taken into account. The text is accepted as original. In this way, legal documents

are implemented privately, or through the "language of the law" it is observed which common interests are part of the legal discourse.

The occurrence of innovations in language required the study of legal speech. The analysis of legal speech led to the emergence of legal discourse in the field of anthropolinguistics. The study of legal discourse contributes to the development of fields such as legal linguistics and linguistic criminalistics. There are several types, these are:

1. Institutional
2. Personal
3. Regarding the court
4. Legal and others.

The following tasks are solved in the legal discourse:

- ___ describe the concept of legal discourse and define its parameters;
- ___ indication of legal means is carried out in the legal text;
- ___ to identify linguistic and extralinguistic factors affecting the interpretation of legal speech;
- ___ describing the metalinguistic essence of the thesaurus;
- ___ semantic, pragmatic, linguistic and cultural study of legal speech;

The text of legal documents is the main object of study of legal discourse. Information is not an influencing function, it reveals the social pragmatic position of the author of the text. The change in the political and legal structure of the state also leads to a change in the position of the subject. Decisions made are studied as a personalized genre. Language tools and its interpretation are very important in describing the legal discourse. Claims, complaints, explanatory letters are used to determine the place of a person in this discourse.

(of the victim and the criminal), it is important to study materials such as documents, reports, response letters from a theoretical, semiotic, lingucultural, sociopragmatic point of view.

According to O.A. Nesterova, the main aspects of text research within the framework of linguistic forensics are as follows:

1. Text analysis is as a carrier of information about events and situations.

2. Assessment of a person or group of persons or their actions

analysis of the text as a carrier of signs. In cases this category is extremist, as well as in cases related to defamation and insult

includes the analysis of texts that are material evidence.

3. Analysis of the text as a speech act. This aspect of the work consists of questions related to identifying the roles and functions of interviewees, signs of threats, incentives and calls to action. [Nesterova, 2019, 261-264]

Based on the development of social sciences, the term subject in legal discourse is a subject that requires its own study and discussion.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that in English, Russian and Turkish linguistics, the role of the individual in legal texts has been studied and recognized, this concept has not yet been studied as a research topic in the Uzbek language, by analyzing the texts, a general definition of the concept of personality is given in the discourse, the status of linguistic personality in legal discourse is studied as a part of the field of anthropolinguistics.

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